

To Study the Generation Gap and Personality Profile's: An Explorative Study

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Abstract:-

Background: Generation gap is a dilemma observed between young people and their older generations due to different variables. There are a number of problems between different generations due to many reasons such as lack of relevance, alternative perspectives, social factors and the impact of innovation difficult to see each other. **Purpose:** The aim of this study was to understand the generation gap and personality profile of individuals amongst different generations in Indian context whereas “Pre-Liberalization Generation” (Pre-1991), “Early Liberalization Generation” (1992-2001), “Rapid Growth Generation” (2002-2006), & “Plateau Growth Generation” (2007-2012) and current generation as “Computer Generation” is been taken and considered to be a part of study. Although various earlier studies revealed that there is a generation gap, so in this research we performed an explorative study in context to six dimensions: *Social Expectation, Economic Development, Distinct attitude, Communication Gap, Education and Technology* with a congruency to generations in Indian context. (Generations are been taken as per Srinivasan earlier study).

Sample & Method: Two hundred fifty individuals from different type of families (125 from nuclear families and 125 from joint families) categorized under five generations completed the GGQ: (A self-administered generation gap questionnaire) to find the generational gap which included 30 questions each onto six dimensions of generation gap taken in our current research study. Correspondingly *personality factors questionnaire (16 P.F.)* was used to find the differences in personality profiles amongst generations.

Tools: As a part of statistical tools being used, we calculated standard deviation and mean of each generation onto dimensions using GGQ Likert scale data. For testing of hypothesis calculation of mean values t-test, one-way ANOVA along with multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) correlating sixteen personality factors (16 P.F. assessment) was used to interpret the scoring and to analyze individual personality to fulfill objective of the study.

Results:

H1 - The study revealed that there is a generation gap using six dimensions: *social expectation, economic development, distinct attitude, communication gap, education and technology* among generations on GGQ.

H2: Study revealed that there is a statistical difference in personality profiles of different type of families (Nuclear and Joint) amongst different generations.

H3: Study revealed that there is a significant difference in personality profiles amongst generations.

Conclusion: 16 P.F. is a useful tool to examine personality profile differences amongst the generations and to understand the factors that build their personalities. Given differences amongst the generations, the researcher forecast possible causes as six dimensions taken in the present study. Suggestive measures are also been disclosed in the study to bridge the gap and to make the individuals personality a dynamic, versatile and to lead happier life head.

Keywords: *Personality traits, Personality factors, Generation gap, Personality profile.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Generation gap has made a crack in familial relationships. A few endeavors and research had been accomplished to understand the vitally causative additives of this difficulty, to try to find out some solutions for a few manners or any other reduce its growing maintain over the rising struggles among numerous generations. The concept of technology gap has existed for pretty some time but over the brand-new years it has come to be extra conspicuous in our fashionable public and is currently being visible and tended to as a massive difficulty of our society. Generation gap affects family members in addition to regular exercises, due to headway of recent advances and lack of correspondence among the younger technology and the extra pro one.

Generation gap interpreted through definition is taken into consideration as a difference amongst near domestic decisions, suppositions and examine of numerous generations which activates clashes and hole among relatives. The generation gap is a difficult issue seen in youth and their senior generations because of different variables. It is seen that it is more among youngsters and guardians; the gap anyway is relied upon to be more extensive if there should be an occurrence of grandparents and grandkids.

The Major three key trends of generation lie between: Parenting, Technology and Economics. Although in this study we took Social Expectation, Economic Development, Distinct attitude, Communication Gap, Education and Technology considering the dimensions in order to find the congruency in a better way.

A. Generation: An overview

The generation gap is also emerging as a communication gap that is once again having a serious impact on adolescent mental health. As interviewed, it also provides an indication that communication barriers play an important role in aggression, stress and anxiety. The generation gap is caused

by longevity, extended life expectancy, rapid social development and social displacement.

- **Generation as per U.S. Demographics:** Classification of generation gap as per U.S demographics is been categorized on the basis of age as “Traditionalist” / “Veterans” – born amid 1925-1940; “Baby boomers” – 1941-1960; “Generation X” – 1961-1976; “Millennia’s” – 1977-1992.
- **Classification Note:** According to the American Society for Human Resource Management (SHRM, 2004), four demographic segments dominate the occupational space, and these segments are reduced by age as follows:
 - Veteran - born 1925-1940;
 - Baby Boomers 1941-1960;
 - Generation X 1961-1976;
 - Millennial 1977-1992.

But each country has its own set of events that are responsible for influencing a generation, or, as has been argued previously, Employee location is an important factor when studying relationships generational demographics in one workspace, and therefore similar in-depth search is needed for Indian audiences. This generational localization combines organisms of a particular generational segment with a common socio-historical background. Based on this understanding, many prominent scholars have proposed the following generational groups in India.

- **Generation as per Indian Context:** Talking about the generational gap and its classification as per Indian context, various researches have provided their inputs on the same. Ghosh & Chaudhari (2009) categorized the current generations of India into three sub-categories – “the conservatives – (1947-1969); Integrators – (1970-1984); Y2K – (1985-1995). Similarly, Srinivasan (2012) suggested four generations as systematic research study which are: “Pre-Liberalization Generation” (Pre-1991), “Early Liberalization Generation” (1992-2001), “Rapid Growth Generation” (2002-2006), & “Plateau Growth Generation” (2007-2012) who started working during or before liberalization in India.

B. Classification Note:

As Per Srinivasan (2012) study suggested four generations as systematic research study, are as-Generation before liberalization (before 1991), Early Liberalization Generation (1992-2001), The period of rapid growth (2002-2006) and The Growth Plateau Generation (2007-2012). Thus, in this present study we have added “Computer Generation” (2013 and later on) as a part of research in congruency to individual’s personality profile and generational gap.

C. Correlation with determinants: A Brief

- **Generational and social expectations:** Both generations expect the other to behave as they do. Both create age-related bias.
- **Generation and Economic development:** Recognizing the need to reduce unemployment, the younger generation must go far. In this situation, she neglects her responsibilities towards her elders. The modern generation should focus on their development, this may

be economic, social or otherwise, but at the same time they must have a positive attitude and show respect to those who his old age because they have different interests, preferences and frequency of thinking.

- **Generation and Distinct attitude:** The traditional generation enjoys books, classical music, walking around with friends and family, and believes in reusing used products. But modern generation likes to spend time on social sites, pop music, nightlife and long car rides etc. Two people with different tastes in music, fashion, marriage, eating habits, culture and politics, etc. The traditional generation probably observed these differences in the modern generation.
- **Generation and education:** The most important difference is that education leads to work, money, lifestyle and fame. In the modern generation, we have all the facilities and opportunities to learn and learn more and more. There are many schools, colleges and universities that help us achieve our educational goals. And the last one leads us to a bright and successful future. But in the mainstream generation, they are educated to understand life not only to achieve the goals of education, work, money, etc.
- **Generation and technology:** Nowadays, our lives are more and more dependent on machines and we are all becoming indifferent to our parents who did most of the daily chores on their own and kept active pole. Children are used to spending most of their time using electronic devices and social media without them finding out their problems with their parents. Internet solves most of the world's problems.

D. Defining Personality:

- **Personality** refers to individual differences in characteristic patterns of thinking, feeling and behaving. The study of personality focuses on two broad areas: One understands individual differences in particular personality characteristics, such as sociability or irritability. The other concept of personality understands how the various parts of a person come together as a whole. Personality explanations can focus on a variety of influences, ranging from genetic explanations for personality traits to the role of environment and experience in shaping an individual's personality.
- **16 P.F. by Raymond Cattell:** According to Cattell, there is a continuum of personality traits. In other words, each person contains all of these 16 traits to a certain degree, but they might be high in some traits and low in others. Cattell developed an assessment based on these 16 personality factors. The test is known as the 16PF Personality Questionnaire and is still frequently used today, especially in career counseling, marital counseling, and in business for employee testing and selection. The test is composed of forced-choice questions in which the respondent must choose one of three different alternatives. Personality traits are then represented by a range and the individual's score falls somewhere on the continuum between highest and lowest extremes. The scores can be interpreted using a number of different

systems, depending upon why the test is being used. Some interpretive reports take a clinical approach looking at personality, while others are more focused on topics such as career selection, teamwork development, and leadership potential. 16PF: The multi-purposed instrument, 16PF or 16 Personality Factors, is used as a career evaluation tool, for couples counseling and personality assessment. 16 PF is used by psychologists and counselors to provide job occupations that best fit the individuals' characteristics. 16 P.F. Contains: 185-item Sixteen Personality Factor Questionnaire (16PF), originally developed by Cattell and Mead (1949), is a **185-item** measure of normal personality which is currently in its fifth edition.

E. Contribution brief:

As a part of contribution, we are adding one more primitive angle of study by including **“Computer Generation” (2013 or later)**, it will lead us to know the better outcome of the personality's psychological views which will be beneficial for further study in current scenario where pandemic has also played a significance role in generational gap and personality profile with an approach of adaptive intelligence and anxiety levels congruency with isolation and other determinants.

II. REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

The review of literature gives an outlook about the research Gap in the existing research. It also strengthens the theoretical base of research study. It has been seen that the more established generation additionally appear to share this nature of uncertainty particularly as their kids get more master with taking care of new advancements and web. Along these lines, in general guardians are sure with regards to the instructive possibilities gave through new advancements yet are simultaneously worried about the negative possibilities of advances and web.

Pundits have expressed and are primarily worried about the senseless hysterias spurred by innovation and the reaction of more seasoned generations which may have built a bogus ideal of the weak kid, which could misdirect investigates and approaches. So, one might say that a large number of the individuals from more seasoned generations can't acknowledge the new advances though most of more youthful generation considers it to be freeing apparatus which serves different freedoms from schooling to profession and numerous different angles that permit's foundation of youth culture. This distinction in conclusions, musings and decisions prompts clashes between their generations and subsequently make a gap. Studies have been done that desire to investigate between generational perspectives.

A review was finished by Asia Pacific Institute of Aging Studies (APIAS), Lingnan University under the initiative of “Prof. CM Chan” and “Prof. David R. Phillips” that zeroed in on building an organization model in connecting colleges, schools and neighborhood networks through a progression of very much organized program that

included preparing studios and social help projects. It was intended to support collaborations and correspondence among youthful and old generations. It was a longitudinal report directed in 2001 and it was named University School Link Partnership Projects (USLP). The results zeroed in on how the youthful and old are commonly benefitted on their social capability. The plan of the program was to cause the two generations to accomplish appointed undertakings and it was obvious that the program decidedly affected correspondence and common comprehension among the members.

“Punita Malik” a research scholar has provided an edge over the generations in the Indian workforce where it was stressed that various generational cohorts and their characteristics, identified in the framework of Indian workforce. Her study provided a view that different generational workforce is the very first step to increase the productivity in a space of generational diversity.

“George C. Patron” found that adolescent growth and social development shape the early development of offspring from preconception through to the post-partum period through distinct processes in male and females. The study of George C. Patron says at a time of great change in forces shaping adolescence, including the timing of parenthood, investment in today's adolescents, the largest cohort in human history will yield great dividends for future generations.

Crandall et al. in their research have shown that parenting factors and parenting techniques are very important in shaping children's cognitive development accelerate cognitive development. Mothers who value achievement, set high standards for achievement, and reward their children for good performance; both boys and girls do well.

Marfatia in her research has shown that the absence of parental warmth, additional rigidity, an overly controlling attitude often from the father, constant arguments between their parents, Isolation and no entertainment channels are some - a number of reasons are responsible for the imbalance among young people in many areas.

Barren and Earls in their study emphasized that unfavorable parent-child relationships and high family pressure are related to children's difficult behavior.

Thapar conducted a study on the value profiles of parents and their children and the generation gap of urban, middle-class Indian parents and their children. The Rokeach Value Survey (Form E) was conducted. He said parents and children care most about family, safety, freedom, self-respect, ambition, honesty, self-control, and help, and are less concerned with values like salvation, love and adult joy, the world of beauty, imagination and have fun. While parents' value structures correspond well to their respective gender stereotypes, children instill an androgynous value profile, reflecting the respective roles of both parents in raising children.

According to Lin (2018), most workplaces are made up of five generations: traditionalists born before 1946, new generation individuals born between 1946-1964, individuals from Generation X was born between 1965-1979, Generation Y individuals were born between 1980 and 1991, and Generation Z individuals were born after 1991. Figure 1 shows the generation distribution in the workplace in 2000 and 2020. As we see in Figure 1, the most representative generation in 2000 was baby boomers with 42%, followed by Generation X 28%, traditionalists 24% and World Y system 6%. A notable shift can be seen in the generation distribution in 2020, Gen Y 35%, Gen X 33%, Boomers 18%, Traditionalists 3% and times first Generation Z 11%.

Twenge (2001b) found that the assertiveness levels of American women increased and decreased with changes in women's social status during the years 1932-1993, Twenge (2000) states that a meta-analysis of US data from the years 1952 to 1993 showed significantly increased levels of anxiety and neurological disorders.

In another study, Twenge (2001a) performed a time-based meta-analysis in which he tested 4,004 American college students by varying outlier scores between student groups to see the broader environmental impact on the socio-cultural aspect of a person's personality. The study by Twenge (2001a) concluded that 1419% of the variants present in the outlier score could be attributed to changes in the birth group.

Various researchers have emphasized the need to address the generational differences that seem to exist in the work values of workers. Recent literature shows that there are many differences in work values between baby boomers and Generation X that lead to conflict (Adams, 2000). The special necessity was highlighted by Fyock, who warned in 1990 that these generational differences can play a role in causing misunderstandings, misunderstandings, and conflicting signals.

It is important to note that the meaning of work has changed dramatically over the course of the decades (Steiner & Steiner, 2000), the sixteenth century saw the development of a Protestant work ethic (Steiner & Steiner, 2000). EPF from the belief that hard work, dedication, frugality, and perseverance are essential to achieving God's joy and are especially important to salvation (Steiner & Steiner, 2000).

However, a significant number of these new innovations which accompany the two chances or dangers are not new to the general public yet its impact is more far and wide and prompts, particularly for youngsters and more youthful generations. The developing innovation can likewise be thought to influence family relationship and could be the significant explanations behind clashes. Web has drawn in a great deal of consideration which has brought up a few issues like disparity, access, the nature of the substance, the ramifications of web and new innovation on youngsters' instructive and social turn of events. It has been seen over many discussions and strategies that in administration and appropriation of web, kids and adolescents are respected with indecision. Being considered

both as the "computerized generation" in internet-based capabilities yet in addition entirely helpless and conceivably in danger. Generations should attempt to disclose their plans to relatives in an easy-going way.

III. RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

After studying the previous researches it is important to understand the current situation whereas we may include the global pandemic situation and the behaviors which generation adapted, tended towards hike in various issues related to mental health and psychological effects as seen globally wide newspapers and government reports along with the hike in number of cases percentage wise in personality, behavior, attitude and dissonance amongst "Pre-Liberalization Generation" (Pre-1991), "Early Liberalization Generation" (1992-2001), "Rapid Growth Generation" (2002-2006), & "Plateau Growth Generation" (2007-2012) - (Generation classification is taken as per Srinivasan (2012) along with a contribution of current generation as "Computer Generation (2013 – Later on)".

Primitive issues have been identified by Psychiatrists and Counselors globally that due to pandemic and isolation amongst generations has tended behavioral changes and overall personality profiles got effected with a change in ideologies related to virtual connections and imaginative mindset. (Hike in number of mental health cases in last 2 years supports the statement). So, there is a need of understanding the current generation personality in context of behaviors and attitudes and their psychology. Need of studying personality profiles is prominent, as it has already been observed in previous studies that the "generation gap is an emerging issue and threat to the society".

Hence an attempt has been made to assess the generation gap and its determinants having congruency with personality profiles. This will help to design appropriate intervention measures to enhance the sense to further study about mental health implications in context to intergenerational gap.

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Problem:

Pandemic and isolation in the current generation has taught us the adaptive intelligence as well said by "Sternberg". Various mental health issues are been seen increasing with a pace due to isolation in the pandemic. This kind of pandemic situation and isolation is been faced by all generations and is found to be problematic for generations to adjust. The present research aims to study the relationship between generation gap and personality profile amongst the "Pre-Liberalization Generation" (Pre-1991), "Early Liberalization Generation" (1992-2001), "Rapid Growth Generation" (2002-2006), & "Plateau Growth Generation" (2007-2012) and along with "Computer Generation" which we added as a part of study for current generation which will lead us towards better understanding of the implications of the study.

B. Objective of the Study:

This research was planned in order-

- To study the generation gap in context to social expectation, economic development, distinct attitude, communication gap, education and technology.
- To study the Personality profiles of different types of families amongst different generations.
- To study the Personality profiles of different individuals amongst different generations.

It is extremely important to better understand the psychology of young people before interacting, interacting, collaborating, connecting and leading as well as engaging with them at home, at school, at work and in life necessary. The research presented shows the prevalence and increasing generation gap, especially in the post-80s and older generations. Understanding the psychology of generations requires an understanding of the differences between different generations. Armed with this understanding will enable us to learn effective means of communication, establish strong positive connections, and maintain generational cultural values. In addition, it is important for young people to understand themselves and the difference between themselves and the previous generation to bridge the generation gap. Current Pandemic has a greater impact as per general view of the society. Observations are generalized that due to extreme isolated environment younger generation had a lack of outdoor activities which tended them to adopt gaming and internet in an excessive nature. Problem with older generation were also seen as a primitive aspect as extreme indulgence in activities performed by younger generation caused a Bias.

C. Hypothesis:

- **H1** - There is a generation gap amongst “Pre-Liberalization Generation” (Pre-1991), “Early Liberalization Generation” (1992-2001), “Rapid Growth Generation” (2002-2006), & “Plateau Growth Generation” (2007-2012) and along with “Computer Generation” on GGQ “*Generation gap questionnaire*”.
- **H2** - There is a statistically significant difference between *personalities* of different types of family amongst generations.
- **H3** - There is a statistically significant difference of *personality profiles* amongst different generations.

D. Research Variable:

In the current research study different generations and type of families is been considered as independent variable and its six determinants along with 16 personality factors as dependent variable.

E. Research Design:

The researcher prepared the questionnaire from the literature review of the related studies naming it as GGQ (Generation gap questionnaire). The research questionnaire after conducting the face validity consists of 6 dimensions, whereas 30 items (Table 2) measuring the generation gap (individual’s perspective in context to determinants of generation gap) amongst generations (as per present study) on Likert-type scale ranging from 1 to 3 where, the researcher used the following criteria to outline the respondent’s response range:

Strongly Disagree (N): 1

Neutral (N.A.): 2

Strongly Agree (Y): 3

Items N	Items*	Dimensions	No.
5	5,3,1,2,4	Social Expectations	1
5	6,9,8,7,10	Economic Development	2
5	15,12,11,13,14	Distinct Attitude	3
5	16,19,17,20,18	Communication Gap	4
5	23,24,21,22,25	Education	5
5	29,26,27,28,30	Technology	6
Total 30		(6) Dimensions	

Table 1: Items distribution on each dimension

*items placed in table 1 are in ascending order as per each questionnaire’s internal consistency result(s).

Personality factors were assessed by using 16 P.F. (fourth and fifth edition) considering general population (Male & female both).

F. Research Setting:

This study is dependent on a specific setting or location since it uses Purposive sampling, hence based on the convenience and availability of the Samples (Nuclear and joint families), the location was selected. The data collected used self-administered questionnaires, all participants were not required to be in one place. The different types of families were approached in their own compatibility area, where they were briefed about the project, its purpose and all the questionnaires were explained in detail. They were told that true and prompt answers were expected and that correct responses shall ensure relevant outcomes.

G. Sample:

A sample is been randomly selected from the Capital of Uttarakhand a small town “THE DOON VALLEY – Dehradun”. Total of 250 individuals (Table: 1 shows the details) are been selected to be a part of the study. Five groups have been taken each consisting of 50 individuals segregated under five categories as – “Pre-Liberalization Generation” (Pre-1991), “Early Liberalization Generation” (1992-2001), “Rapid Growth Generation” (2002-2006), & “Plateau Growth Generation” (2007-2012) and current generation as “Computer Generation (2013 – Later on)”.

Type of Family -->	Nuclear	Joint	Total
Generations			
Pre-Liberalization (Pre - 1991)	18	32	50
Early (1992-2001)	19	31	50
Rapid (2001-2006)	22	28	50
Plateau (2006-2012)	28	22	50
Computer (2013-Lateron)	38	12	50
Total	125	125	250

Table 2: Sample Details

H. Sampling Technique:

Non-Probability sampling method is been used in the present study along with purposive sampling.

I. Methods of Data Collection:

A proper Documentation was prepared prior to the commencement of data collection activity. It included a Demographic detail form and Project brief along with the questionnaires for the individuals amongst different generations. Through references and personal approach to different type of families say nuclear and joint were contacted. After which the project purpose and objectives were explained. All queries were resolved which was enquired by the respondents. Respondents were asked to feel absolutely relaxed and free of any unwanted thoughts before filling in their responses. Doubts & queries around the tests were resolved before the responses were collected. Assurance of confidentiality of information was provided and maintained. Purpose of the study and instructions of the tools, was explained before administration of the questionnaires. The respondent(s) were told that true and correct responses were to be shared to ensure good outcomes. The data collected thus, was analyzed and compared to achieve the objectives of the study, subsequently using appropriate statistics the research hypothesis was tested.

J. Data Collection Tools:

The Demographic questionnaire, Generation Gap questionnaire, 16 P.F. Personality factor questionnaire was used to assess generation gap and personality profile and with an explorative study approach.

- **Demographic Questionnaire** is designed in order to get the general information such as: name, age date of birth marital status, education experience of the respondent between different types of families amongst different generations taken as a part of study.
- **Generation gap questionnaire (GGQ)** – An individual face to face interview with questionnaire related to various determinants of generation gap - social expectation, economic development, distinct attitude,

communication gap, education and technology was assessed. The Scale is designed to assess generation gap on various determinants taken in the study. Time taken to complete the GGQ is 5 minutes approximately. The language used is English and in addition verbally regional language was used to explain the specific question if required. The responses are rated on 3 Point Likert-type scales ranging from 1 to 3.

- **Instrument 16 PF:** As (16 P.F.) measures the primary components of personality. In the present study it was used to assess the personality profile/traits amongst generations which provided a clear picture of the real scenario if generation gap has affected the personality profile of an individual's under different generations in its determinants. Time taken varies from and 30 – 45 minutes. The Language used is Hindi with norm table as general population (male & female) is been used in order to assess the personality profile of 250 respondents amongst generations taken as a part of current study.

K. Reliability:

- **GGQ** It was measured through Alpha Cronbach by measuring internal consistency for each questioner dimensions (**0.35 - 0.68**), and the internal consistency of the questioner (**0.80**). Table 3 shows the result.

Dimensions	Result	No.
Social Expectations	0.35	1
Economic Development	0.68	2
Distinct Attitude	0.53	3
Communication Gap	0.56	4
Education	0.58	5
Technology	0.43	6
Total	0.80	7

Table 3: The result of the questionnaire reliability

- **16 P.F.** is reported to have good reliability.
- **Data Analysis:** Descriptive as well as Inferential statistics was used for data analysis in the proposed study.
- **Statistics Used:** The analysis involved Mean, Standard Deviation, T – test, analysis of variance -ANNOVA and multivariate analysis of variance - (MANOVA) for testing of hypothesis.
- **Simple Percentage Analysis:** Simple percentage analysis is one of the basic statistical tools which is widely used in the analysis and interpretation of the main data. It deals with the number of respondents’ response to a particular question in percentage arrived at the total. Simple percentages is used in the study to analyze the factors like demographic and other details of the respondents.
- **T-Test:** The independent sample t-test is used when two separate sets of independent and identically distributed samples are obtained, one from each of the two groups/populations being compared.
- **ANOVA:** Analysis of variance (ANOVA) is a statistical technique that is used to check if the means of two or more groups are significantly different from each other.

ANOVA checks the impact of one or more factors by comparing the means of different samples.

- **MANOVA:** In statistics, multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) is a **procedure for comparing multivariate sample means**. As a multivariate procedure, it is used when there are two or more dependent variables, and is often followed by significance tests involving individual dependent variables separately.

V. RESULT and DISCUSSION

- **Internal Consistency:** We have prepared used GGQ (Generation gap questionnaire) in order to find the generation gap related to the six dimensions social expectation, economic development, distinct attitude, communication gap, education and technology. Questionnaire reliability is been measured through Alpha Cronbach. Table shows the result as internal consistency for each questioner dimensions as **(0.35 - 0.68)**, and the internal consistency of the whole questioner as **(0.80)** which is observed as good for the current study.

Alpha Cronbach	Results
	30.00
Sum of Variance	57.72
Internal Consistency	0.80

Table 3

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.801	.801	30

Fig. 1

After performing normality test researcher observed that Sig. value of the Shapiro-Wilk test is greater than .05, hence concluded that the data is normal. Q-Q plots also shows that data is normally distributed.

Tests of Normality

Generation	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Respondent Pre - 1991	.065	50	.200 [*]	.956	50	.058
Early - (1992-2001)	.065	50	.200 [*]	.956	50	.058
Rapid - (2002-2006)	.065	50	.200 [*]	.956	50	.058
Plateau - (2007-20012)	.065	50	.200 [*]	.956	50	.058
Computer - (2013 - Lateron)	.065	50	.200 [*]	.956	50	.058

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Table 4

- Q-Q plots for different generations:

Graph 1

Further testing homogeneity of variances the p significant value was observed more than .05 hence met the assumption of homogeneity of variance. In order to test H1 in a significant way we used One-way analysis of variance

ANOVA using SPSS in order to interpret the results amongst generations using GGQ. Under descriptive statistics we observed the mean values and standard deviation with following interpretations:

Descriptives

Respondent	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Pre - 1991	50	25.50	14.577	2.062	21.36	29.64	1	50
Early - (1992-2001)	50	75.50	14.577	2.062	71.36	79.64	51	100
Rapid - (2002-2006)	50	125.50	14.577	2.062	121.36	129.64	101	150
Plateau - (2007-20012)	50	175.50	14.577	2.062	171.36	179.64	151	200
Computer - (2013 - Lateron)	50	225.50	14.577	2.062	221.36	229.64	201	250
Total	250	125.50	72.313	4.573	116.49	134.51	1	250

Table 5

ANOVA

Respondent	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1250000.000	4	312500.000	1470.588	<.001
Within Groups	52062.500	245	212.500		
Total	1302062.500	249			

Table 6

We computed sum of squares between groups and within groups having numerator as 4 and denominator as 245 with a d.f. value as 249 obtaining the result using SPSS whereas f ratio = (1470.58) and p ratio as (< .001) which concluded that p value/ ratio is statistically significant (p < .05). Thus, NULL Hypothesis is rejected and can strongly say that there is a statistical difference between generations taken in the present study.

- **(H2):** We performed 16 P.F. assessment of 250 individuals in order to find the difference in personalities of different type of family (Nuclear and Joint) in generations. We categorized the family into two groups ascertaining types of family as *Nuclear family and Joint family* under 5 generations taken as a part of current study.

Graph 2: Bar graph shows the categorization

As a part of current study, types of family – Two groups (nuclear and joint families) under different generations were taken as independent variables whereas 16 personality factors were treated as dependent variable.

Further from main data we performed reliability statistics using SPSS and found the overall questionnaire reliability as (0.70) which is in acceptable condition under Cronbach's Alpha.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.705	16

Fig. 2

A standardized format is used for administering the 16 PF for data collection. We administered the 16 PF fourth edition to respondents during the data collection that occurred between 1989 – 1996 because the 16 PF underwent an update in 1994, we used the 16 PF fifth edition for subsequent data collection from respondents accordingly. Research has shown that fourth and fifth edition of 16 PF measures the same traits. We used 16 PF raw scores and further used SPSS in order to analyze differences in response to the 16 PF using a multivariate analysis of variance model for different type of family with the significance level (p value) set at (< .001). A multivariate analysis of variance MANOVA and the Post hoc analysis was used to analyze the differences in responses to the 16

PF for nuclear family and joint family a generation cohort. 16 PF factors used in analysis were – Warmth, Reasoning, Emotional Stability, Dominance, Liveliness, Rule-Consciousness, Social Boldness, Sensitivity, Vigilance, Abstractedness, Private-ness, Apprehension, Openness to Change, Self-Reliance, Perfectionism, and Tension. Descriptive statistics is been analyzed through SPSS software along with the estimation of effect size was observed under partial ETA squared field. A report on Comparison of Means was interpreted using SPSS whereas joint family and nuclear family along with 16 personality factors were observed. After interpreting the means of different types of family onto 16 P.F. scale we can normally observe that there is a difference between the mean level.

Report

Type of Family		Warmth	Reasoning	Emotional Stability	Dominance	Liveliness	Role-Consciousness	Social Boldness	Sensitivity	Vigilance	Abstractedness	Private-ness	Apprehension	Openness to Change	Self-Reliance	Perfectionism	Tension
Nuclear Family	Mean	4.00	4.06	4.03	4.18	4.16	3.82	3.55	3.69	3.51	3.53	4.21	4.30	4.07	4.58	4.11	4.19
	N	125	125	125	125	125	125	125	125	125	125	125	125	125	125	125	125
	Std. Deviation	1.586	1.605	1.818	1.855	1.793	1.807	1.838	1.907	1.785	1.907	2.197	2.005	1.837	1.960	2.025	1.970
Joint Family	Mean	2.90	3.42	3.10	2.95	3.14	2.74	2.85	2.85	2.97	2.72	2.85	2.88	2.90	3.33	3.28	3.70
	N	125	125	125	125	125	125	125	125	125	125	125	125	125	125	125	125
	Std. Deviation	1.595	1.747	1.708	1.655	1.770	1.576	1.676	1.587	1.601	1.599	1.603	1.664	1.750	2.023	1.686	1.906
Total	Mean	3.45	3.74	3.57	3.57	3.65	3.28	3.20	3.27	3.24	3.12	3.43	3.59	3.48	3.95	3.69	3.94
	N	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250
	Std. Deviation	1.681	1.705	1.821	1.860	1.851	1.775	1.790	1.800	1.714	1.803	2.072	1.972	1.885	2.088	1.907	1.950

Table 7

Descriptive Statistics				
	Type of Family	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Warmth	Nuclear Family	4.00	1.586	125
	Joint Family	2.90	1.595	125
	Total	3.45	1.681	250
Reasoning	Nuclear Family	4.06	1.605	125
	Joint Family	3.42	1.747	125
	Total	3.74	1.705	250
Emotional Stability	Nuclear Family	4.03	1.818	125
	Joint Family	3.10	1.708	125
	Total	3.57	1.821	250
Dominance	Nuclear Family	4.18	1.855	125
	Joint Family	2.95	1.655	125
	Total	3.57	1.860	250
Livelihood	Nuclear Family	4.16	1.793	125
	Joint Family	3.14	1.770	125
	Total	3.65	1.851	250
Rule-Consciousness	Nuclear Family	3.82	1.807	125
	Joint Family	2.74	1.576	125
	Total	3.28	1.775	250
Social Boldness	Nuclear Family	3.55	1.838	125
	Joint Family	2.85	1.676	125
	Total	3.20	1.790	250
Sensitivity	Nuclear Family	3.69	1.907	125
	Joint Family	2.85	1.587	125
	Total	3.27	1.800	250
Vigilance	Nuclear Family	3.51	1.785	125
	Joint Family	2.97	1.601	125
	Total	3.24	1.714	250
Abstractedness	Nuclear Family	3.53	1.907	125
	Joint Family	2.72	1.599	125
	Total	3.12	1.803	250
Privateness	Nuclear Family	4.21	2.197	125
	Joint Family	2.65	1.603	125
	Total	3.43	2.072	250
Apprehension	Nuclear Family	4.30	2.005	125
	Joint Family	2.88	1.664	125
	Total	3.59	1.972	250
Openness to Change	Nuclear Family	4.07	1.837	125
	Joint Family	2.90	1.750	125
	Total	3.48	1.885	250
Self-Reliance	Nuclear Family	4.58	1.969	125
	Joint Family	3.33	2.023	125
	Total	3.95	2.088	250
Perfectionism	Nuclear Family	4.11	2.025	125
	Joint Family	3.26	1.686	125
	Total	3.69	1.907	250
Tension	Nuclear Family	4.19	1.970	125
	Joint Family	3.70	1.906	125
	Total	3.94	1.950	250

Table 8

Further under general linear model we performed Box's Test of Equality of Covariance Matrices^a in order to test the null hypothesis that the observed covariance matrices of the dependent variables are equal across

groups. We interpreted f – value as 1.424 with a significance level of alpha as <.001 which means that we can reject the null hypothesis. The plot observed is as under:

Fig. 3

Multivariate analysis of variance is been used in order to determine whether the 16 personality factors tends to have a significant role under different types of family amongst generations. Using the data sheet under IBM SPSS software we computed the results which shows that we can reject the null hypothesis although multivariate results are considered to be the most important aspect while

interpreting the result in a clear sense. Only after analysing the results performing multivariate test homogeneity we can say that there is statistically significant difference between *personalities* of different types of family (Nuclear and Joint) amongst generations. Below is the output retained from Multivariate Test output using IBM SPSS Software.

Multivariate Tests^a

Effect		Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared	Noncent. Parameter	Observed Power ^c
Intercept	Pillai's Trace	.972	496.679 ^b	16.000	233.000	<.001	.972	7946.865	1.000
	Wilks' Lambda	.028	496.679 ^b	16.000	233.000	<.001	.972	7946.865	1.000
	Hotelling's Trace	34.107	496.679 ^b	16.000	233.000	<.001	.972	7946.865	1.000
	Roy's Largest Root	34.107	496.679 ^b	16.000	233.000	<.001	.972	7946.865	1.000
TypeofFamily	Pillai's Trace	.431	11.049 ^b	16.000	233.000	<.001	.431	176.792	1.000
	Wilks' Lambda	.569	11.049 ^b	16.000	233.000	<.001	.431	176.792	1.000
	Hotelling's Trace	.759	11.049 ^b	16.000	233.000	<.001	.431	176.792	1.000
	Roy's Largest Root	.759	11.049 ^b	16.000	233.000	<.001	.431	176.792	1.000

a. Design: Intercept + TypeofFamily

b. Exact statistic

c. Computed using alpha = .05

Table 9

Whereas, results of MANOVA yielded that there was a statistically significant difference between the groups on the combined dependent variable, *Wilk's Lambda* value is been observed as (.569) with a *f*-value as 11.049 along with *p* – value as < .001; based on the results evidence was sufficient to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that respondent of

different types of family have different personality profiles as measured on 16 P.F. (Raymond B. Cattell's) scale.

H3 Statistical Analysis of the data: We used 16 P.F. in order to find the difference in personality profiles amongst different generations. Further results are been interpreted on using multivariate analysis of variance in order to statistically prove our hypothesis (H3).

Between-Subjects Factors

		Value Label	N
Generations	1	Pre 1991 Gen	50
	2	Early 1992-2001	50
	3	Rapid 2002-2006	50
	4	Plateau 2007-2012	50
	5	Computer 2013- Lateron	50

Table 10

Results are been interpreted using IBM SPSS to analyze the data. Under general linear model we performed Box's Test of Equality of Covariance Matrices^a in order to test the null hypothesis that the observed covariance

matrices of the dependent variables are equal across groups. We interpreted *f* – value as 1.226 with a significance level of alpha as <.001 which means that we can reject the null hypothesis. The plot observed is as under:

Box's Test of Equality of Covariance Matrices^a

Box's M	775.191
F	1.226
df1	544
df2	104457.561
Sig.	<.001

Tests the null hypothesis that the observed covariance matrices of the dependent variables are equal across groups.

a. Design: Intercept + Generations

Fig. 4

Descriptive statistics is been analyzed through SPSS, from where mean and standard deviation are been interpreted. Table Shows output obtained:

Descriptive Statistics				
	Generations	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Warmth	Pre 1991 Gen	3.46	1.717	50
	Early 1992-2001	4.02	1.857	50
	Rapid 2002-2006	3.46	1.669	50
	Plateau 2007-2012	3.30	1.555	50
	Computer 2013- Lateron	3.00	1.485	50
	Total	3.45	1.681	250
Reasoning	Pre 1991 Gen	3.62	1.806	50
	Early 1992-2001	4.36	1.535	50
	Rapid 2002-2006	3.42	1.642	50
	Plateau 2007-2012	3.74	1.724	50
	Computer 2013- Lateron	3.56	1.716	50
	Total	3.74	1.705	250
Emotional Stability	Pre 1991 Gen	3.96	1.414	50
	Early 1992-2001	4.00	2.060	50
	Rapid 2002-2006	3.80	2.070	50
	Plateau 2007-2012	2.98	1.684	50
	Computer 2013- Lateron	3.10	1.581	50
	Total	3.57	1.821	250
Dominance	Pre 1991 Gen	4.18	1.859	50
	Early 1992-2001	3.74	1.712	50
	Rapid 2002-2006	3.56	2.052	50
	Plateau 2007-2012	3.48	1.681	50
	Computer 2013- Lateron	2.98	1.939	50
	Total	3.57	1.860	250
Liveliness	Pre 1991 Gen	3.86	1.948	50
	Early 1992-2001	3.56	1.809	50
	Rapid 2002-2006	3.84	1.856	50
	Plateau 2007-2012	3.92	1.893	50
	Computer 2013- Lateron	3.06	1.671	50
	Total	3.65	1.851	250
Rule-Consciousness	Pre 1991 Gen	3.78	1.833	50
	Early 1992-2001	3.20	1.604	50
	Rapid 2002-2006	3.10	1.644	50
	Plateau 2007-2012	3.22	1.972	50
	Computer 2013- Lateron	3.10	1.776	50
	Total	3.28	1.775	250
Social Boldness	Pre 1991 Gen	3.82	1.561	50
	Early 1992-2001	3.52	1.876	50
	Rapid 2002-2006	3.10	1.919	50
	Plateau 2007-2012	2.78	1.765	50
	Computer 2013- Lateron	2.78	1.632	50
	Total	3.20	1.790	250
Sensitivity	Pre 1991 Gen	3.46	1.887	50
	Early 1992-2001	3.56	1.971	50
	Rapid 2002-2006	3.52	1.843	50
	Plateau 2007-2012	3.20	1.604	50
	Computer 2013- Lateron	2.60	1.552	50
	Total	3.27	1.800	250
Vigilance	Pre 1991 Gen	4.10	1.418	50
	Early 1992-2001	3.30	1.810	50
	Rapid 2002-2006	3.30	1.972	50
	Plateau 2007-2012	2.82	1.521	50
	Computer 2013- Lateron	2.68	1.477	50
	Total	3.24	1.714	250
Abstractedness	Pre 1991 Gen	3.76	1.611	50
	Early 1992-2001	3.26	1.957	50
	Rapid 2002-2006	2.98	1.964	50
	Plateau 2007-2012	2.94	1.731	50
	Computer 2013- Lateron	2.68	1.596	50
	Total	3.12	1.803	250
Privateness	Pre 1991 Gen	3.40	1.829	50
	Early 1992-2001	2.88	1.899	50
	Rapid 2002-2006	4.24	2.404	50
	Plateau 2007-2012	4.10	2.341	50
	Computer 2013- Lateron	2.52	1.216	50
	Total	3.43	2.072	250
Apprehension	Pre 1991 Gen	3.74	1.816	50
	Early 1992-2001	3.74	2.155	50
	Rapid 2002-2006	4.10	1.972	50
	Plateau 2007-2012	3.74	2.039	50
	Computer 2013- Lateron	2.64	1.588	50
	Total	3.59	1.972	250
Openness to Change	Pre 1991 Gen	3.52	1.972	50
	Early 1992-2001	3.42	1.679	50
	Rapid 2002-2006	4.10	1.810	50
	Plateau 2007-2012	3.72	2.100	50
	Computer 2013- Lateron	2.66	1.586	50
	Total	3.48	1.885	250
Self-Reliance	Pre 1991 Gen	4.18	1.815	50
	Early 1992-2001	4.06	2.004	50
	Rapid 2002-2006	5.06	2.054	50
	Plateau 2007-2012	3.82	2.249	50
	Computer 2013- Lateron	2.84	1.695	50
	Total	3.95	2.088	250
Perfectionism	Pre 1991 Gen	3.68	1.778	50
	Early 1992-2001	3.86	2.020	50
	Rapid 2002-2006	4.34	1.780	50
	Plateau 2007-2012	3.40	2.148	50
	Computer 2013- Lateron	3.16	1.621	50
	Total	3.69	1.907	250
Tension	Pre 1991 Gen	3.86	2.050	50
	Early 1992-2001	3.96	2.089	50
	Rapid 2002-2006	4.68	1.720	50
	Plateau 2007-2012	4.02	1.964	50
	Computer 2013- Lateron	3.20	1.678	50
	Total	3.94	1.950	250

Table 11

A report on Comparison of Means was interpreted using SPSS whereas different generations along with 16 personality factors were observed. Below table shows the report:

		Report															
Generations		Warmth	Reasoning	Emotional Stability	Dominance	Liveliness	Rule-Consciousness	Social Boldness	Sensitivity	Vigilance	Abstractness	Privateness	Apprehension	Openness to Change	Self-Reliance	Perfectionism	Tension
Pre 1991 Gen	Mean	3.46	3.62	3.96	4.18	3.86	3.78	3.82	3.46	4.10	3.76	3.40	3.74	3.52	4.18	3.68	3.86
	N	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50
	Std. Deviation	1.717	1.806	1.414	1.859	1.948	1.833	1.561	1.887	1.418	1.611	1.829	1.816	1.972	1.815	1.778	2.050
Early 1992-2001	Mean	4.02	4.36	4.00	3.74	3.56	3.20	3.52	3.56	3.30	3.26	2.88	3.74	3.42	4.06	3.86	3.96
	N	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50
	Std. Deviation	1.857	1.535	2.060	1.712	1.809	1.604	1.876	1.971	1.810	1.957	1.859	2.155	1.679	2.004	2.020	2.089
Rapid 2002-2006	Mean	3.46	3.42	3.80	3.56	3.84	3.10	3.10	3.52	3.30	2.98	4.24	4.10	4.10	5.06	4.34	4.68
	N	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50
	Std. Deviation	1.669	1.642	2.070	2.052	1.856	1.644	1.919	1.843	1.972	1.964	2.404	1.972	1.810	2.054	1.780	1.720
Plateau 2007-2012	Mean	3.30	3.74	2.98	3.48	3.92	3.22	2.78	3.20	2.82	2.94	4.10	3.74	3.72	3.62	3.40	4.02
	N	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50
	Std. Deviation	1.555	1.724	1.684	1.681	1.893	1.972	1.765	1.604	1.521	1.731	2.341	2.039	2.100	2.249	2.148	1.964
Computer 2013- Lateron	Mean	3.00	3.56	3.10	2.88	3.06	3.10	2.78	2.60	2.68	2.68	2.52	2.64	2.66	2.84	3.16	3.20
	N	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50
	Std. Deviation	1.485	1.716	1.591	1.803	1.671	1.776	1.632	1.552	1.477	1.596	1.216	1.588	1.586	1.695	1.621	1.678
Total	Mean	3.45	3.74	3.57	3.57	3.65	3.28	3.20	3.27	3.24	3.12	3.43	3.59	3.48	3.95	3.69	3.94
	N	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250
	Std. Deviation	1.681	1.705	1.821	1.860	1.851	1.775	1.790	1.800	1.714	1.803	2.072	1.972	1.885	2.098	1.907	1.950

Table 12

After interpreting the means of different generations onto 16 P.F. Scale we can normally observe that there is a difference between the mean level. Multivariate analysis of variance is been used in order to determine whether the 16 personality factors tends to have a significant role under different generations. Using the data sheet under IBM SPSS

software we computed the results which shows that we can reject the null hypothesis although multivariate results are considered to be the most important aspect while interpreting the result in a clear sense. Below are the multivariate results:

Multivariate Tests ^a									
Effect		Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared	Noncent. Parameter	Observed Power ^d
Intercept	Pillai's Trace	.963	370.832 ^b	16.000	230.000	<.001	.963	5933.318	1.000
	Wilks' Lambda	.037	370.832 ^b	16.000	230.000	<.001	.963	5933.318	1.000
	Hotelling's Trace	25.797	370.832 ^b	16.000	230.000	<.001	.963	5933.318	1.000
	Roy's Largest Root	25.797	370.832 ^b	16.000	230.000	<.001	.963	5933.318	1.000
Generations	Pillai's Trace	.550	2.319	64.000	932.000	<.001	.137	148.434	1.000
	Wilks' Lambda	.547	2.347	64.000	902.685	<.001	.140	146.793	1.000
	Hotelling's Trace	.664	2.370	64.000	914.000	<.001	.142	151.690	1.000
	Roy's Largest Root	.283	4.120 ^c	16.000	233.000	<.001	.221	65.919	1.000

- a. Design: Intercept + Generations
- b. Exact statistic
- c. The statistic is an upper bound on F that yields a lower bound on the significance level.
- d. Computed using alpha = .05

Table 13

Whereas, results of MANOVA yielded that there was a statistically significant difference between the groups on the combined dependent variable, *Wilk's Lambda* value is been observed as (.607) with a *f-value* as 2.347 along with *p-value* as <.001; based on the results evidence was sufficient to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that respondent of different generation have difference in personality profiles as measured on 16 P.F. (Raymond B. Cattell's) scale.

VI. CONCLUSION

The result of our exploratory study reveals that there is a generation gap in context to the determinants of our study observed from the responses on generational gap questionnaire related to social expectation, economic development, distinct attitude, communication gap, education and technology determinants. In different generations older adults and youths faced and observed the prima phase changes which tended them to adopt the change as per the need of an hour. Various studies have already

revealed the cohorts of generational gap, in this present study it was revealed that but obvious differences were due to the dimensions taken as a part of study. The present study also revealed that there is a greater impact on personality profile of an individual due to different type of family environment under different generations. As we found that there is a generational gap which again plays a vital role in deciding the personality profile of an individual. Hence, we concluded from the current study that although generation gap does exist but there is a major role of this generational gap in deciding personality profiles of an individuals. Even type of family residing has been observed to have changes in personalities of individuals under generations. Serious mental health cases are been administered and found misunderstanding, lack of understanding, dominance, communication gap and much more. There are remedial measures quoted in the present study in order to bridge the gap and to understand the need of an hour to think over it and to adopt the changes arises due to other determinants such as technological changes economic development etc.

VII. STRENGTHS AND LIMITATIONS

A. Strengths:

This is one of the studies reported where the differences in the generations were compared to personality factors along with determinants of generation gap collectively in purview of people residing under nuclear and joint families. Personality profiles were assessed through 16 PF the reliable personality assessor which is worldwide used by psychologists to assess the personality as its quite reliable tool used in the current study. Tool used to measure generation gap was a self-administered questionnaire whose congruency was to relate the determinants of generation gap. Questionnaire reliability was administered and observed good. Data were collected by a single investigator, thereby decreasing the chance of inter observer variations.

B. Limitations:

Limitation of the study is that the generation gap was observed using a relatively small sample size. Personality profile of the sample size was just used in reference to check the overall difference between generational cohort rather than to focus onto a primitive angle resulting to the major personality factor which tends the change and adoption of trait due to generation gap. As the researcher got opportunity to meet only the 'survivor population' which may be the constraint. Lastly, as the data was collected using a nonnormative sampling methodology where data was normally collected although it was purposive but, findings may not be generalizable to whole population size as it was targeted within Dehradun city limits.

VIII. SUGGESTIONS

Based on research findings, future studies can be much more beneficial if generation gap can be studied in an elaborative manner using 16 PF and finding the overall factor responsible to be the primitive major cause in tending personality profile's due to various determinants of generational gap. As looking forward in order to bridge the generation gap various researchers have already discussed about the same but here is a need to ascertain in the context whether this generational gap is tending the cause for anxiety depression in the prima phase. Generation gap and personality profiles can be studied in an elaborative manner in congruency to emergence of stress anxiety and depressive symptoms under current generations as parents and childhood conflict cases are at their pace as reported under MOHFW survey.

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